

PLANT TISSUE AND DNA BIOBANK – METADATA STANDSRDS

Taxonomic information:

- i. Scientific name and taxonomic authority
- ii. Taxonomic classification (including family, order and higher ranking as relevant)
- iii. Common name (if known)

Collection information:

- i. Collection date (day, month, year) when the sample was collected.
- ii. Primary collector's name and institution. Include full names of all persons or teams involved in the collection of the sample(s)
- iii. Collection site details, include the name of the specific site, reserve or geographic area where the sample(s) were collected.
- iv. GPS Coordinates: Latitude and longitude (in decimal degrees) of the precise location where the sample was collected.
- v. Elevation/Altitude: The elevation or altitude (in meters) at the collection site.
- vi. Habitat Description: provide a brief description of the habitat or ecological zone where the sample was collected (e.g., grassland, forest, wetland).
- vii. Geopolitical Location – provide details of province, and nearest locality or landmark where the sample was collected.
- viii. Collection Method – give a description of the method(s) used to collect the plant tissue or to extract the DNA sample.
- ix. Provide relevant environmental data at the time of collection, including temperature, humidity, rainfall, soil type.
- x. Any observable traits or characteristics of the plant, including morphological descriptions.

Preservation and Storage Information

- i. Description of how the sample was preserved at the time of collection (e.g., dried with silica gel, stored in ethanol, frozen).

Legal and Ethical Documentation

- i. Provide reference numbers and details of all permits required for collecting the sample (e.g., local, national, international permits).
- ii. Evidence of informed consent or benefit-sharing agreements with indigenous communities or landowners, where applicable.
- iii. Documentation of compliance with the Nagoya Protocol on Access and Benefit-sharing, if applicable.

Other related data

- i. Information on any herbarium voucher specimens that correspond to the DNA or tissue sample, including the herbarium accession number and repository.
- ii. Where available, provide details on any prior DNA extraction or sequencing efforts, including sequence identifiers in open access/public platforms such as GenBank.
- iii. Any photographs of the plant at the time of collection, the habitat, and the specific part of the plant used for tissue sampling.
- iv. Terms under which the sample metadata and associated data can be shared with researchers and institutions, e.g., open access, for restricted access (please indicate the cutoff date for the embargo as all samples in the Biobank must eventually be open access).
- v. Citations or references to any publications that have used the sample in prior research.
- vi. Research purpose – provide information on the intended use of the sample (e.g., DNA barcoding, phylogenetic studies, conservation research).

Review Process:

- i. All metadata submissions will undergo review by the Biobank staff to ensure completeness and accuracy before accessioning the sample.
- ii. Samples lacking required metadata may be conditionally accepted with follow-up required or rejected outright until sufficient metadata is provided.